

Enhance Chatter Prediction for Increased Productivity

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Abstract

Milling process instability due to regenerative chatter vibrations is a complex phenomenon that has been causing serious damages and imposing productivity limits in the manufacturing industry. Developing a reliable solution that complies with the practical capacities of a shopfloor brings economic and environmental benefits. This paper introduces a physics-supported probabilistic machine learning approach, where chatter monitoring data from one or multiple machines are effectively exploited under a federated learning scheme, also enabling the attained knowledge to be transferred to other machines and processes. The resulting probabilistic prediction offers added reliability by revealing unresolved uncertainties due to limited observation through arbitrary cuts. The approach offers extended applicability for chatter prediction in non-rectangular workpiece-tool interactions, which often occur in industrial milling. The effectiveness is evaluated through experimental case studies and shows a promising solution to the decades-old industry's struggle with the chatter issue.

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1 Introduction

Chatter vibrations severely limit the productivity of all kinds of chipping machines threatening with severe damage on tool, workpiece or even machine. Since the pioneering study on regenerative chatter by Tlustý [1] in 1963, a lot of effort has been spent to first understand the phenomenon and then find an industrially viable solution for safe avoidance though going to the possible limits or even shifting them. With the stability lobe diagram (SLD) stemming from the zero-order solution (ZOS) by Altintas and Budak [2] a powerful means to distinguish stable and unstable parameter regions. For its setup cutting force coefficients (CFCs) and the frequency response function (FRF) at the tool tip are required, but due to changeover of the machine tool, wear and aging these are prone to considerable uncertainties. The setup of a reliable SLD is for machine tool users infeasible. In recent times artificial intelligence is applied in combination with the physics of SLDs. Postel et al. [3] used the ZOS supported by inputs from multiple artificial neural networks. Each network represents a specific component of the milling system Wegener et al. [4] proposed a modular model of the milling system, augmented with neural networks to account for unmodeled dependencies. To enhance the reliability of the predictions a probabilistic approach proved to be beneficial, as demonstrated by Schmitz et al. [5]. Ostad Ali Akbari et al. [6] improved the underlying physics-based model, specifically the critical model of holder-tool assembly with a distributed joint interface. This enhancement enabled effective information flow between various substructures, enabling federated and transfer learning. Additionally, they demonstrated how model uncertainties could be leveraged to guide experimental data collection through active learning. An extension of the approach from [6] to non-rectangular workpiece-tool interactions is also presented in this paper.

2 Physics-based modeling for chatter stability analysis

To establish a comprehensive modeling framework that accommodates the vast variety of milling system configurations, the system is decomposed into subsystems, each representing a crucial player in process stability as illustrated in **Figure 1**. The advantage of this approach lies in enabling the dedicated refinement of subsystems based on their participation in various machines and processes. Moreover, the refined model of each substructure from one learning iteration can be transferred to new milling operations using transfer learning. Further details are explained in [6].

Figure 1: Modular representation of a milling system for stability analysis through physics-driven modeling.

This modular framework allows for a substructure coupling approach to combine the dynamics of different structural components, ultimately determining the FRFs at the tip of the end mill. Considering **Figure 2**, this is done using the following equation [6]:

$$\Phi_{SHT,11} = \Phi_{HT,11} - \Phi_{HT,21}(\Phi_{HT,22} + \Phi_{S,33})^{-1}\Phi_{HT,21} \quad (1)$$

Regarding the notation, the receptance matrix $\Phi_{HT,21}$ is a 2-by-2 frequency-dependent complex-valued matrix that contains translational and rotational FRFs of the assembly HT when the excitation is applied at point 1 and the response is measured at point 2. This approach is known as Receptance Coupling Substructure Analysis (RCSA) and is explained in detail in [7].

Figure 2: Substructuring approach for tooltip dynamics calculation.

The translational dynamics at the tooltip in X and Y directions $\Phi_{SHT,11,tF}$ are then used in the ZOS to analyze chatter stability, which is based on delayed feedback characterized in the following equation:

$$\det[\mathbf{I} - \frac{1}{2}K_{tc}\Delta a_p \sum_{i=0}^{N_e-1} \mathbf{A}_{0,i} (1 - e^{-sT}) \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{SHT,11,tF}] = 0 \quad (2)$$

With K_{tc} standing for tangential CFC and T for tooth passing period. The above expression includes a summation over directional coefficients to extend the applicability of the ZOS to general workpiece-tool interactions, where the engagement is discretized into N_e elements of rectangular engagement with the thickness Δa_p , as demonstrated in **Figure 3**. The directional coefficient for each element $\mathbf{A}_{0,i}$ is computed using its corresponding engagement angles of $\phi_{st,i}$ and $\phi_{ex,i}$, according to the formulation in [8]. Therefore, the cumulative load from all these elements is substituted into the transfer function of the closed-loop self-excited vibrations. This method is further explained by Budak et al. [9].

Figure 3: Discretized engagement for modeling a non-rectangular workpiece-tool engagement.

3 Bayesian learning and inference

Unlike the deterministic perspective which considers a definite value for a variable, the Bayesian perspective accounts for the entire spectrum of possible variable values along with their realization probabilities. Bayes' rule refines the probability distribution of model parameters according to their agreement with the training data through a likelihood function. The Bayesian learning framework in this study is based on [6], where the detailed model parameters and their distributions are outlined. To briefly recap the core equations, the Bayes rule

$$P(\theta|D) \propto P(D|\theta)P(\theta) \quad (3)$$

considers the following likelihood function to refine the prior $P(\theta)$ to the posterior $P(\theta|D)$, combining information from the stability state of stable cuts plus the information from the stability state and chatter frequency of unstable cuts:

$$P(D|\theta) = \prod_{i=0}^N [P(s_i = 0|a_{cr,model}) + P(s_i = 1|a_{cr,model})P(f_{c,i}|f_{c,model})] \quad (4)$$

where s_i stands for the experimental stability state of a cut with 0 being stable and 1 being unstable. The experimental chatter frequency is $f_{c,i}$. The likelihood from an unstable observation is established based on a sigmoid function using the difference between the model-predicted critical depth of cut $a_{cr,model}$ and the experimental axial depth of cut a_p with the hyperparameter k that adjusts the transition steepness:

$$P(s_i = 1|a_{cr,model}) = 1/(1 + \exp(\frac{a_{cr,model} - a_p}{k})) \quad (5)$$

and for a stable cut $P(s_i = 0|a_{cr,model}) = 1 - P(s_i = 1|a_{cr,model})$. In addition, for unstable cuts, the likelihood of a chatter frequency is computed according to a normal distribution centered around the mean value of the model-predicted chatter frequency $f_{c,model}$, with a hyperparameter standard deviation σ as:

$$P(f_{c,i}|f_{c,model}) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp[-\frac{(f_{c,i} - f_{c,model})^2}{2\sigma^2}] \quad (6)$$

In the end, the inference of the stability state at each process configuration can be computed through the following Monte Carlo estimations:

$$P(s^* = 1|D) = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j=0}^{N_s} P(s^* = 1|\theta_j) \quad (7)$$

and analogously for chatter frequency:

$$P(f_c^*|D) = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j=0}^{N_s} P(f_c^*|\theta_j) \quad (8)$$

These approximations are based on N_s samples of model parameters θ_j drawn with respect to their posterior distributions, for which an Evolutionary Markov Chain Monte Carlo (EMCMC) method is used in this study [10].

4 Applications and validations

The following steps provide a roadmap for deploying the proposed learning system to refine chatter prediction in an industrial environment. The following steps are required for establishing the learning framework:

1. Establish a database to store the geometrical dimensions of the holder and tool. This could be a simple tabular database or be connected to an existing database that some manufacturing companies already use. Alternatively, a camera can be placed inside the tool magazine to automatically detect the necessary dimensions through image processing. This information is used to create a model based on Timoshenko beam elements [11] and compute the dynamics of the holder-tool assembly.
2. Conduct impact tests once per machine tool by mounting a cylindrical dummy holder to the machine's spindle interface, as instructed in [12]. Characterize the machine tool dynamics by mathematically subtracting the effects of the dummy holder to obtain the machine tool FRFs at the spindle flange. Alternatively, approaches such as the machine tool dynamics identification using forced vibrations can be employed to obtain these FRFs [13].
3. Install a microphone on each machine tool for chatter detection through process noise analysis and record the chatter frequency at each instant.
4. Simulate workpiece-tool interaction based on the workpiece geometry and the NC program to calculate the interaction of the tool with the workpiece. Dedicated software packages are available for this purpose. Within the scope of this paper, the workpiece has negligible flexibility compared to the tooltip.

Figure 4: Probabilistic stability analysis for a single machine and process configuration. a) Prior stability inference and b) Posterior after training on indicated experimental data.

The validation of the proposed approach begins with the scenario illustrated in **Figure 4**, where a 3-axis milling machine with the detailed holder-tool combination performs validation cuts on an AL6082 workpiece block. **Figure 4-a** shows the prior probabilistic stability prediction without any experimental data training, revealing a high degree of uncertainty when relying solely on the physics-based model. In **Figure 4-b**, the highlighted points represent the training data used for Bayesian learning to refine model uncertainties. This demonstrates that incorporating even a small amount of training data can enhance the stability prediction accuracy, with the remaining uncertainty indicated by the gray regions.

The case study in **Figure 4** relied only on data collected from a single machine-holder-tool configuration and process. However, having a network of machine tools in a production line offers a valuable opportunity for multiple machines to learn from each other. In the case study in **Figure 5**, federated learning considers a machine tool with three different holder-tool combinations simultaneously in the learning process. Two of these combinations use a similar holder, thereby sharing their holder-tool joint parameters. Additionally, all three cases

use similar tools and cut the same material, allowing them to link their CFCs. The refined model and posterior parameters can then be transferred to a new milling scenario, enabling it to have a more accurate prior prediction.

Figure 5: Federated learning by including three different structural arrangements. After training, model parameters are transferred to a different process for stability prediction.

Figure 6: Posterior stability predictions from federated learning.

The resulting improvement from federated learning with limited training data is shown in Figure 6, illustrating the effectiveness of learning when multiple machines interact during training. The model is then transferred for stability prediction in a non-rectangular engagement. As seen in Figure 7, the proposed approach effectively predicts stability for non-uniform engagements.

Figure 7: a) Transfer learning for stability prediction in non-rectangular workpiece-tool interaction, b) Surface quality and chatter marks on the workpiece surface after performing the validation cuts.

5 Conclusion

Despite extensive research on chatter suppression and various aspects in modeling, a robust, comprehensive, industry-friendly solution suitable for shop-floor implementation is still lacking. This paper adopts the promising strategy of physics-informed Bayesian learning and expands it to include general workpiece-tool interactions. The experimental studies have demonstrated the efficacy of the proposed method, while taking considerations for industrial implementation into account.

6 References

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